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HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF DESERTIFICATION IN KARAKALPAKSTAN, UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. Desertification has been one of the most severe Central Asian environmental concerns, and Karakalpakstan is one of the most affected regions. Its causes go back to the mid-20th century, when Soviet planning redirected the Amudarya and Syrdarya rivers on a large scale to boost cotton production. These actions greatly reduced the quantity of water that flowed into the Aral Sea, leading to a rapid contraction of the sea and triggering profound ecological alterations. As the sea retreated, vast areas of the former sea bed came out, salted and polluted with toxic residues, which became cradles of permanent dust and salt storms. These operations accelerated land degradation, reduced the fertility of the soil, and undermined

conventional agriculture and pastoralism systems. The socio-economic effects have also been extreme: decreased agricultural production, eroding living standards, and increasing health problems for the population. Desertification in Karakalpakstan has progressively become a localized environmental issue and an all-around environmental, economic, and social crisis.

The paper reconstructs the history of desertification in Karakalpakstan from the Soviet era to the present. By analyzing the prolonged ecological and socio-economic shifts, the study underscores the necessity for implementing sustainable land and water use to help avert further

degradation and improve regional resilience against desertification.

Key words: *Desertification, Karakalpakstan, Amudarya, Aral sea, Soil Salinity.*

Introduction. Productive land is vital for human survival, but climate change and unsustainable human activities are driving widespread desertification, especially in already dry regions. Growing demands for food have expanded intensive agriculture, often leading to soil erosion and aquifer depletion through excessive irrigation. Since the 1980s, desertification has affected around 500 million people, worsening poverty, food insecurity, water scarcity, biodiversity loss, forced migration, and vulnerability to climate change. Combatting it requires long-term, coordinated strategies, including:

- Restoration of degraded land
- Sustainable water and land management
- Conservation and rehabilitation efforts (Kassas et al., 1995).

Desertification specifically refers to land degradation in drylands and now impacts 25% of Earth's land and nearly 20% of the global population. Key degradation processes include vegetation loss, erosion, salinization, and soil compaction. These result in a long-term decline in ecosystem services essential for life. Tools like satellite remote sensing and NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) are used to monitor vegetation changes and track desertification.

Scientific frameworks like the Dryland Development Paradigm help guide policy and research by addressing the complex social, ecological, and

economic dimensions of drylands. A 1984 reassessment identified 4.5 billion hectares—about 35% of Earth's land—as at risk, affecting up to 470 million people, mostly in developing countries. The most severely affected regions are in tropical semiarid and sub-humid zones. Desertification remains one of the most serious environmental challenges, demanding urgent, multidisciplinary responses to secure sustainable livelihoods and land use for future generations. (Dregne, 2002).

METHODOLOGY

This research adopts a combined historical–analytical method in examining the role of the Amudarya River and its dams in desertification in Karakalpakstan and situates these findings in the wider picture of global land degradation. Secondary data sources provide the basis for this research, including scientific papers, hydrological data, government reports, and international environmental assessments. First, data on the Amudarya River's flow regime, water diversion projects, and damming were studied, with particular attention to Soviet-era irrigation expansion that reduced water input to the Aral Sea drastically. Archival information and official reports were studied to trace the historical trajectory of water policy and its environmental effect. Second, field survey and remote sensing-based hydrological and ecological research studies were examined to assess land cover change, soil salinity, and vegetation degradation in the region. These studies provided measurable indicators of desertification related to reduced river runoff. Finally,

comparative examination was done with international reports of United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD) and similar case studies worldwide. In this manner, the research was capable of situating desertification in Karakalpakstan within both a regional outcome of Amudarya water mismanagement and as part of overall global environmental challenges.

Results

Desertification affects all continents except Antarctica, threatening the livelihoods of millions—particularly the poor in arid regions. It occurs in drylands, which cover 41% of Earth's land and were home to over 2 billion people in 2000. Defined as land degradation in arid, semi-arid, and dry sub-humid regions caused by human activities, desertification reduces the biological productivity of agricultural and pasture lands. Its severity ranges from 10–25% loss in productivity (moderate) to over 50% loss (severe). Although deserts border many drylands, desertification is not simply the expansion of deserts, but a degradation process influenced by climate variability and land misuse (Wang & Jenkins, 2003). Global soil erosion now exceeds natural replenishment by up to 100 times, mainly due to poor agricultural practices. Nearly 953 million

hectares of land are affected by salinity, limiting productivity. Dry and semi-arid regions, especially in Australia and Asia, contain most salt-affected soils and brackish groundwater, which accelerate desertification. Between 1982 and 2015, 6% of global drylands underwent desertification, driven by unsustainable land use and climate change. Despite various initiatives, the UNCCD has not met its land restoration goals (Ahmed et al., 2024).

The geographic classification of drylands is often based on the aridity index – the ratio of average annual precipitation amounts to potential evapotranspiration amount (Figure 1). Recent estimates, based on aridity index, suggest that drylands cover about 46.2% of the global land area. Hyper-arid areas, where the aridity index is below 0.05, are included in drylands, but are excluded from the definition of desertification. Deserts are valuable ecosystems geographically located in drylands and vulnerable to climate change. However, they are not considered prone to desertification. Low average precipitation or water availability is a long-term climatic condition known as aridity. Therefore, drought, a transient meteorological phenomenon, is not the same as aridity.

Figure 1: Global Aridity Map Showing Drylands (Hyper-Arid, Arid, Semi-Arid, and Sub-Humid Regions) [34].

Desertification stems from the long-term imbalance between the demand for and supply of ecosystem services in dry regions. As desert ecosystems struggle to provide essentials like food, water, fuel, and construction materials, both human activities and climate change intensify the pressure. Direct drivers include unsustainable land use practices and climate-related events (e.g., droughts), while indirect factors involve population growth, policy issues, and global market distortions. Notably, global warming is expected to reduce freshwater availability. In Central Asia, temperatures have risen steadily since the early 20th century, affecting ecosystems, agriculture, and human health (Lioubimtseva et al., 2005). Additionally, land-use changes like deforestation, farm mechanization, and large-scale land-cover modification have increased soil erosion and degradation. These

changes highlight the need to assess land degradation using remote sensing technologies (Abbas et al., 2022).

Africa and Asia account for over 70% of all dryland areas (Figure 2). If deserts are not included, grasslands make up the largest land use/cover in drylands in terms of area, followed by forests and croplands. Therefore, the majority of hyper-arid regions are deserts, with a few minor outliers, such as croplands and grasslands that are irrigated and grown in oasis conditions. Moreover, grasslands are defined as meadows and permanent pastures that have been used consistently for longer than five years. Some of the sites that fall under the category of "other land" are also utilized as non-permanent pastures since transhumance, or periodic migratory grazing, frequently results in non-permanent pasture systems in drylands.

Figure 2: Dryland categories over the world (1980-2015) [34]

Desertification in Central Asia: Key trends and Drivers

Between 2015 and 2019, the world lost over 100 million hectares of productive land annually—more than the combined area of the five Central Asian countries (420 million hectares). This global trend is mirrored in Central Asia, where ecosystems have warmed and humidified at twice the global average rate from 2000–2020 (Weiskopf et al., 2020). A key regional focus is the Aral Sea Basin, spanning nearly 1.8 million km² and shared by seven countries: Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan, Afghanistan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Iran. Historically, 83% of its water flow came from the USSR-controlled regions, with Afghanistan and Iran contributing just 9% (Micklin, 2002).

Desertification in Central Asia is driven by:

- Climate change and rising temperatures (Lioubimtseva et al., 2005)
- Soil salinization, erosion, and poor land use (Hamidov et al., 2016)
- Expanding agriculture and mechanization
- Large-scale deforestation
- Water diversion projects for irrigation and hydropower

The desiccation of the Aral Sea is the most dramatic example. Since the 1960s, water diversion from the Amu Darya and Syr Darya rivers has caused:

- 23-meter drop in water level
- 74% loss in surface area
- 90% reduction in volume
- alinity increases from 10 to 100 g/L
- ollapse of native fish species and

deltaic ecosystems

- Dust and salt storms impacting climate and health (Micklin, 2006)

Dust haze affects cities in the region, with 10–20 haze days annually, yet little research exists on dust's effect on urban environments (Shukurov et al., 2024).

Although the Aral Sea crisis is severe, its underlying causes—unsustainable land and water use—are shared with many other arid and semi-arid regions worldwide.

The desiccation of the Aral Sea since the 1960s is one of the most well-documented cases of anthropogenic ecological destruction. The loss of the sea has deeply impacted livelihoods, health, and ecosystems in the region, highlighting the interconnectedness of human systems and the environment (White, 2013). The Aral Sea Basin, covering 1.76 million km², spans multiple Central Asian countries—99% of Tajikistan, large parts of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, northern Afghanistan, and part of Iran. Its climate is extremely continental, with hot summers, cold winters, and less than 200 mm of annual precipitation, making it heavily dependent on river inflows (Chen et al., 2022).

Environmental Consequences

The shrinking of the Aral Sea has:

- Eliminated its climate-buffering role, causing harsher

winters and hotter summers

- Increased dust storms, spreading toxic salts and pesticides

- Accelerated desertification and soil degradation

- Destroyed biodiversity, including the extinction of 20+ native fish species, collapsing the fishing industry (Plotnikov et al., 2023)

The creation of the Aralkum Desert—formed from the dried seabed—has worsened wind erosion and air pollution. Deltaic wetlands have also declined, threatening migratory bird habitats and ecological balance. The environmental crisis has triggered severe health problems: Respiratory and kidney diseases, and cancers from toxic dust (Anchita et al., 2021) High infant mortality and malnutrition from contaminated drinking and irrigation water. Collapse of agriculture and fisheries has led to widespread poverty and outmigration

Governments have struggled to mitigate the crisis due to limited resources and overwhelming economic costs. Kok-Aral Dam in Kazakhstan, which has partially restored the North Aral Sea, improving water levels, fish stocks, and local livelihoods Regional cooperation initiatives via the International Fund for Saving the Aral Sea (IFAS) and UNDP, promoting **water conservation, afforestation, and sustainable agriculture**

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Figure 3: Map of Uzbekistan

The northwest region of Uzbekistan is home to the autonomous republic of Karakalpakstan. With a total area of about 164,900 km², it is Uzbekistan's largest administrative region. It shares borders with Turkmenistan to the south and Kazakhstan to the north and west. It is located between latitudes 41° and 46° N and longitudes 56° and

62° E. Its eastern border is traversed by the Amu Darya River, one of Central Asia's principal water sources.

The severe continental climate of Karakalpakstan is distinguished by: Summers from June to August are hot and dry, with highs of 45°C. Winters that are cold (December to February), with lows of -20°C.

Table 3: Monthly Average Temperature (°C) in Chimbay Weather Station (1990–2024) [35]

Temperature	1990	1995	2000	2007	2010	2015	2020	2024
January	-4,2	-2,4	-1,9	0	-3,4	-2,3	-0,6	-4,5
February	-1,5	0,4	1,3	1,2	-4,9	-0,2	3,4	0,8
March	7,6	5,1	6	4,7	6,7	4,4	8,7	12,5
April	13,7	17,4	18,5	15,3	15,1	14,8	14,4	16,8
May	20,9	21,3	20,6	22,2	22	22,6	23,1	21,9
June	27,3	26,5	25,4	26,3	28,4	28,7	27,4	27,5
July	27,4	29	28,2	27,8	28,4	29	29,3	30,1
August	24,8	26	27,3	26,8	27	25,3	25	26,8
September	20,9	19,4	19,4	20,3	19,5	19,7	18,3	19,3
October	11	11,3	9	11,7	13,8	10,7	11,2	13,2
November	6	8	2,2	4,5	7,2	4,3	2	9,4
December	-3,2	-3,2	0,5	-3,5	0,9	2	-5,8	-0,1

Table 3 shows a year-to-year trend in temperature, which indicates an overall increase in temperatures, particularly during summer months, where temperatures have been increasing steadily. For instance, July temperatures have risen from 27.4°C in 1990 to 30.1°C in 2024, with an increasing trend due to long-term climatic shifts. The same can be observed during spring and autumn seasons, where there is a marginal increase in temperature, with an overall warming trend throughout the year. However, winter months contain more variability with no visible trend. Although there are less harsh winters in certain years, others see even record-low temperatures

being registered. Temperatures in January, for example, ranged between -4.2°C in 1990 and -4.5°C in 2024, and there is no pattern in trends of cold season. Such abnormalities may be because of short-term atmospheric change, global weather patterns change, or local climatic conditions.

Low yearly precipitation leads to arid and semi-arid conditions, usually below 100 mm. strong winds that propel dust storms, mainly because of Aral Sea desiccation. Because of low rainfall and high evaporation, aggravating soil salinization and vegetation loss, the climate is a significant factor in desertification and land degradation.

Table 4: Monthly Precipitation Trends in Chimbay (1990–2024) (mm)[35]

Precipitation	1990	1995	2000	2007	2010	2015	2020	2024
January	12,3	10,6	19,3	4,1	9,5	11,7	5,7	2
February	12	8,5	5,6	4,9	26,2	19,5	11,9	9
March	11,6	13,3	8,3	42,3	4,2	21,2	5,9	4
April	13,5	19,5	9,5	23,9	10,4	13,6	21,5	11
May	3,6	5,2	3,7	1,7	5,7	26,6	16,3	17
June	4	3	4,4	1,6	0,6	0,1	1,1	0
July	3,7	2,4	2,4	2,6	4,8	0,9	3,5	1
August	0,9	0,3	3,8	1,7	1,6	0,5	3,2	4
September	0,6	4,5	5	0	0	0	0	6
October	23,8	3,7	14,4	3,4	3,6	15,1	0	18
November	13,3	3,3	4,4	4,2	0,9	21,3	6,3	6
December	15,7	4	15,2	17	0,7	14	2,7	19

Table 4 presents a summary of precipitation behavior over Chimbay between 1990 and 2024, both seasonal variations and long-term changes in rain regimes. While no apparent rising or declining trend can be seen, information proves to show

remarkable fluctuations across some years and months.

Winter months (Dec to Feb) are generally months of moderate rains, with less frequent peaks like in January 2000 and December 2024. The spring months (March to May) are really unpredictable, sometimes experiencing heavy rain

(March 2007 recording 42.3 mm) and sometimes extremely dry (May 2007 recording a measly 1.7 mm). Summer months (June to August) record the lowest precipitation values, often close to zero, indicating a dry period characteristic of this region. Exceptions do occur, such as heavy rain in June 2015 and July 2020. Autumn months (September to November) record irregular trends with certain months experiencing heavy rainfall (October 1990 and November 2015), while others remain dry (September 2020). This means that autumn precipitation trends are more random, perhaps due to changing weather patterns. Overall, the precipitation data suggests the randomness of rainfall in Chimbay, with sporadic extreme values that can be explained by local or global climate conditions, including El Niño events, changes in atmospheric circulation, or local weather pattern adjustments. Understanding these differences is crucial for water resource management, agriculture, and climate adaptation planning in the region. The terrain of Karakalpakstan is primarily composed of plateaus and level desert plains, with three main geographical features: The Ustyurt Plateau is a high, limestone plateau in the west that stretches into Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan. It is extremely dry and has little vegetation. Part of the largest desert in Central Asia, the Kyzylkum Desert is located in the east and is distinguished by patches of hardy shrubs and sand dunes.

Aral Sea Basin: Aral Sea, which was once one of the biggest inland lakes in the world, has

drastically reduced in size, revealing the Aralkum Desert, a vast area of salty plains. The Amu Darya River dominates the hydrology of the area; it supplies irrigation water for farming but has experienced excessive diversion, resulting in water shortages. As shown in Figure 4, the study area is located in the southern part of the Aral Sea, where people live.

Socioeconomic and Environmental Challenges in the Karakalpakstan

There are several challenges in this area, some of which are extremely critical and urgently require solutions.

First, the drinkable water is almost a poison. The amount of salt in the water is four times more than what the World Health Organization advises. Along with a high proportion of heavy metals, the Amu Darya and Sir Darya waters contain trash from pesticides and fertilizers. Furthermore, the Amu Darya's new canal in Afghanistan is being drugged, which could eventually result in a shortage of fresh water.

Secondly, the salt crust covering the soil and climate change have rendered thousands of hectares unusable for agriculture. One of the most crucial issues for reviving the Aral Sea economy is this. The fishing industry is the third main issue facing the Aral Sea economy. Fishing prospects in the area are decreasing these days. Because the Aral Sea is too distant from the original shore, fisherman cannot access the harbors at Moynak and Aralks. Due to this fact, the unemployment rate has increased and is now among the highest in the Uzbekistan Republic.

The study area, Karakalpakstan, has a population of approximately 1.9 million people, comprising a diverse mix of ethnic groups including Karakalpaks, Uzbeks, Kazakhs, and Turkmens. The city of Nukus serves as the administrative, economic, and cultural center of the region. The capital and largest city of Karakalpakstan is Nukus, and the country is administratively separated into 15 districts. Beruniy, Kungrad, Khodjeyli, and Moynaq are other significant urban centers. Although Uzbek and Russian are also widely spoken, the Karakalpak people have their own language and traditions, giving the area a unique cultural identity.

The solution for the economically matters is very difficult because agriculture and fishery are among the main activities of the Karakalpak economy while industry counts less than 10% of the total employment.

These are not the only repercussions; the people in this area have also experienced a number of illnesses. Karakalpakstan has one of the highest death rates in the world, and the birth rate, which was once among the highest in Central Asia, has now decreased as well. This can be explained by the deterioration of medical issues.

Figure 5: Historical Population of the Karakalpakstan

Figure 5 shows population growth in Karakalpakstan between 1979 and 2020, illustrating a steady increase in population year after year. The population increased at an exponential rate of +2.99% per annum during the period from 1979 to 1989. While decreasing at a rate of +1.96% per annum, 1989–2000

was the decade of sustained growth.

The growth rate went further down to +0.83% per year during the next decade, 2000–2010, when the population growth settled down. But from 2010 to 2020, again the growth rate increased by

+1.52% per year, indicating population growth accelerated once more.

Historical Context of Land Use and Water Management

Karakalpakstan is located in the lower reaches of the Amudarya River, in the south-east corner of the Ustyurt plateau, the southern part of Aral Sea and the Amudarya delta, and the western part of the Kyzyl-Kum desert. The Amudarya and Syr Darya flows into Aral Sea have significantly decreased as a result of the present ineffective agricultural methods. The Ministry of Agriculture and Water Resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan currently irrigates 97,917 hectares of the 1,682,411 hectares of land

resources in Southern Karakalpakstan, of which approximately 250,650 hectares are deemed suitable for irrigation. Primitive agriculture, particularly on-farm irrigation and reclamation systems and irrigated fields, dominates the majority of the Republic of Karakalpakstan's irrigated lands. A wide area is covered by irrigated areas, and the land-use factor value is between 0.65 and 0.70. There are sizable areas of undeveloped land that are unsuitable for irrigation within the irrigated land contour. Particularly on-farm irrigation systems are too long, have a tortuous plan, and have an efficiency rating of no more than 0.65 to 0.66 (Kurbanbaev et al., 2021).

Figure 6: Annual water flow in the Amudarya River from 1931 to 2020

Figure 6 shows a dramatic declining trend in the Amudarya River's water discharge from 1931 to 2020. While the river discharge fluctuated in the range of 1000-

2000 km³ from year to year during the mid-20th century, an abrupt and consistent decline began in the 1970s. The water flow fell heavily by the 1980s and barely crossed the 500 km³ threshold thereafter. This

trend clearly indicates the heightened stress on the river water resources, most likely due to rising irrigation demand, climate change, and inefficient water management practices. Reduction in flow has a far-reaching impact on agriculture, ecosystem stability, and the ongoing desertification process in the region.

Table 5 presents annual water use statistics of the Amu darya River for the years 1990-2020, both monthly and annual average. The statistics reveal high variability in water consumption over the years. For instance, the early 1990s, between the years 1991 and 1994, record very high water consumption with some years exceeding 500 million m³ as an average per year. This overlaps with the final years of the Soviet Union and the transition in Central Asia and likely reflects uncontrolled or poorly controlled irrigation projects. Following 1995, there is an apparent decrease in the average water use, with some years such as 2001 and 2008 having very low values, suggesting either improved management of water or reduced water availability. Water consumption peaks re-appear occasionally, e.g., in 2005 and 2010, possibly due to agricultural demand or drought response. The most recent records, between 2015 and 2020, show more stable and generally reduced water usage, possibly reflecting the effects of water conservation policy and changing climatic conditions. The averages also reveal seasonal trends, with the peak usage typically occurring in summer months like June to August, which are also the principal irrigation seasons. The seasonal spread reflects the intensive

use of the river for the production of crops in the region.

Conclusion

The Karakalpakstan desertification example illustrates one of the most dramatic examples of human–environment interaction in Central Asia. Analysis of long-term climatic trends indicates that both temperature rise and precipitation changes have exerted impacts on environmental strain in the area. However, this study indicates that the reduction in flow of the Amudarya River is the most important cause of desertification. The Amudarya was historically the lifeline of Karakalpakstan, supporting agriculture, habitats, and local livelihoods. But upstream massive irrigation projects, gigantic dam constructions, and reckless water management have altered its flow significantly.

This diminished river discharge has caused a cascade of environmental impacts. Reduced water inflow has continued to expand the shrinkage of the wetlands and drying up of the Aral Sea, revealing extensive expanses of salty terrain in return. Wind erosion and salt and dust storm expansion have also further degraded the land further, presenting very harsh challenges in agriculture and human health. Vegetation loss, salinization of land, and diminished biodiversity are its immediate manifestations, while the socioeconomic impacts such as migration, unemployment, and lowering of standards of health confirm the way desertification has become not only an ecological but a humanitarian problem too.

Table 5: Annual water usage in the Amudarya River Basin from 1990 to 2020 (km³)

Year	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December	Average
1990	66,9	33,4	29,3	109	109	297	393	352	364	413	246	283	218
1991	612	263	88,2	142	259	433	251	378	576	578	186	157	327
1992	566	197	270	127	1190	1790	1930	1400	813	294	497	105	765
1993	190	179	391	214	389	1390	1250	381	554	371	215	366	490
1994	481	395	421	426	137	273	1580	1350	909	573	294	254	591
1995	430	134	109	39,3	18,3	16,6	42,7	63,6	85,3	130	89,5	73,2	103
1996	29,8	39,1	19,2	39,3	64,4	163	487	198	234	325	199	64	155
1997	48,8	57,1	12,1	7	21,1	16,6	15,7	16,9	21,6	30,3	20	13,1	23,4
1998	10,7	121	52,1	55,1	1160	2010	1600	1260	605	347	205	172	633
1999	131	90	129	48	23,2	50	75	114	228	347	152	205	133
2000	296	105	35	25,9	23,3	17,9	5,75	5,5	4,56	4,51	4,08	2,85	44,2
2001	2,58	2,48	3,16	3,55	3,08	3,43	3,27	3,07	3,31	3,64	3,08	3,77	3,2
2002	3,41	3,46	3,01	2,38	4,57	395	384	39,4	152	23,3	55,7	170	103
2003	202	14,9	21,3	216	709	961	912	43,4	93,5	93,6	15,9	78,9	280
2004	82,2	147	72,2	88,9	161	600	328	14,6	67,3	18,3	11,9	19,3	134
2005	82,5	334	156	429	354	457	2150	566	431	144	56,7	133	441
2006	124	245	275	58,8	27,3	48,6	21,5	27,5	60,3	48,6	16,5	50,2	83,6
2007	15,3	11	5,81	5,01	6,83	25	51	20,7	8,6	12,3	34,7	21,2	18,1
2008	10,9	56,1	12,2	5,89	6,07	5,41	5,17	4,99	3,06	3,4	4,14	4,54	10,2
2009	4,85	5,38	6,96	6,63	11,3	39,4	101	397	129	120	83,9	87,6	82,8
2010	169	33,7	71,1	202	1070	800	1270	1470	699	354	132	132	534
2011	27,9	27,1	25,8	11,3	10,5	12,2	15,8	13,9	12,4	11,2	33	23,5	18,7
2012	32,8	43,7	103	186	219	236	1050	128	235	151	124	172	223
2013	203	54	48,8	19,4	17,8	18,9	33,3	35,9	55	47,3	36,4	31,7	50,1
2014	46	50,7	21,2	17,8	19,3	22,5	36	38,2	36,9	48,6	28,2	21	32,2
2015	31,9	26,5	38,3	96,7	45,1	17	343	859	353	107	184	272	198
2016	138	70,4	53,1	58,3	12,2	38	86,1	42,6	47,1	50,2	44,2	33,5	58,1
2017	37,1	34,7	28,1	73,5	333	1018	581	97,3	205	84	29,3	27,1	212
2018	28	20	44	8,66	8,33	8,66	9	5	5	5	11,3	19	14
2019	6,93	13,5	26	28	46,6	25,9	29,3	177	116	36	72,6	74	53,6
2020	32,4	45	51,3	40	38,5	38,7	37,9	27,1	23,9	23,9	27,6	unknown	32,9

The research confirms that while climate variability does play some role, it is anthropogenic lowering of the flow of the Amudarya that has remained the primary cause of desertification in Karakalpakstan. The historical trajectory of this

development emphasizes the need for immediate transboundary water management, regional cooperation, and sustainable land planning in order to restore ecological balance. Deserts will continue to spread and threaten the environment and well-being of future generations in

Karakalpakstan and much further beyond unless action is taken to regulate water allocation and improve resource governance.

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**EKOLOGIYA VA AHOLI SALOMATLIGI XARITALARINI
YARATISHDA ARCGIS DASTURINING IMKONIYATLARI**

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola O'zbekiston hududida o'sma (saraton) kasalliklarining tarqalishini epidemiologik-statistik tahlil va GIS asosidagi kartografik vizualizatsiya orqali ochib beradi. Maqsad — kasallanish va o'lim ko'rsatkichlarining hududiy notekisligini aniqlash, xavf omillariga ishora beruvchi hamda sog'liqni saqlashga qaratilgan tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish. Ma'lumotlar bazasi sifatida GLOBOCAN, WHO country profiles, O'zbekiston SSV yillik hisobotlari va ochiq ma'lumotlardan foydalanildi. Mazkur maqolada O'zbekiston bo'yicha saraton kasalliklarining statistik ko'rsatkichlari, ularning viloyatlar kesimidagi hududiy

taqsimoti va GIS xaritalash orqali tahlili yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: O'sma kasalliklari, saraton, GIS, kartografiya, epidemiologiya, onkologik statistika, GLOBOCAN, O'zbekiston, hududiy tahlil, sog'liqni saqlash, kasallanish ko'rsatkichi, o'lim ko'rsatkichi, xavf klasteri, skrining, sog'liq siyosati, makon-vaqt tahlili, ma'lumot vizualizatsiyasi, barqaror sog'liqni rejalashtirish.

O'sma kasalliklari bugungi kunda butun dunyo miqosida jiddiy ijtimoiy va tibbiy muammolardan biri bo'lib, ularning tarqalishi va o'lim ko'rsatkichlari yildan-yilga ortib bormoqda. Jahon sog'liqni saqlash tashkiloti ma'lumotlariga ko'ra,